

Article

Rhythm analysis during cardiopulmonary resuscitation using convolutional neural networks

Iraia Isasi ^{1,*}, Unai Irusta ¹, Elisabete Aramendi ¹, Trygve Eftestøl ², Jo Kramer-Johansen ³ and Lars Wik ³

¹ Department of Communications Engineering, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, 48013 Bilbao, Spain; irai.isasi@ehu.eus (I.I.); unai.irusta@ehu.eus (U.I.); elisabete.aramendi@ehu.eus (E.A.)

² Department of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, University of Stavanger, 4036 Stavanger, Norway; trygve.eftestol@uis.no (T.E.)

³ Norwegian National Advisory Unit on Prehospital Emergency Medicine (NAKOS), Oslo University Hospital and University of Oslo, 0424 Oslo, Norway; jo.kramer-johansen@medisin.uio.no (J.K.J.), lars.wik@medisin.uio.no (L.W.)

* Correspondence: irai.isasi@ehu.eus (I.I.); Tel.: +34-946-01-73-86

Version May 14, 2020 submitted to Entropy

Abstract: Background: Chest compressions during cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) induce artifacts in the ECG that may provoke inaccurate rhythm classification by the algorithm of the defibrillator. The objective of this study was to use convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to design a shock/no shock decision algorithm reliable during CPR. Methods: A cohort of 3319 ECG segments of 9 sec extracted during chest compressions were used, whereof 586 were shockable and 2733 nonshockable. Chest compression artefacts were removed using a Recursive Least Squares (RLS) filter, and the filtered ECG was fed to a CNN classifier with three convolutional blocks and two fully connected layers for the shock/no-shock classification. A 5-fold cross validation architecture was adopted to train/test the algorithm, and the process was repeated 100 times to statistically characterize the performance. The proposed architecture was compared to the most accurate algorithms that include handcrafted ECG features and a random forest classifier (baseline model). Results: The median (90% confidence interval) sensitivity, specificity, accuracy and balanced accuracy of the method were 95.8% (94.6-96.8), 96.1% (95.8-96.5), 96.1% (95.7-96.4) and 96.0% (95.5-96.5), respectively. The proposed algorithm outperformed the baseline model by 0.6-points in accuracy. Conclusion: This new approach shows the potential of deep learning methods to provide reliable diagnosis of the cardiac rhythm without interrupting chest compression therapy.

Keywords: Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA), cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), electrocardiogram (ECG), adaptive filter, deep learning, machine learning, convolutional neural network (CNN), random forest (RF) classifier.

1. Introduction

Out of hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) is one of the leading causes of death worldwide [1,2]. The two key life saving therapies are defibrillation (electric shock) when the cardiac rhythm is ventricular fibrillation (VF) or tachycardia (VT), and cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) [3]. The defibrillator monitors the electrocardiogram (ECG), and includes a shock/no-shock algorithm that analyzes the patient's ECG to detect VF/VT [4]. The American Heart Association (AHA) has established the minimum accuracy requirements for these algorithms [5]. Shockable rhythms should be detected with a minimum sensitivity (Se) of 90% to properly identify defibrillation treatment conditions. The specificity (Sp) for detection of nonshockable rhythms must be above 95% to avoid unnecessary shocks that may damage the myocardium or deteriorate the quality of CPR.

30 The mechanical activity of chest compressions during CPR induces artifacts in the ECG that
31 impede a reliable shock/no-shock decision by the defibrillator [6]. Therefore, defibrillators prompt the
32 rescuers to stop chest compressions for rhythm analysis every 2 minutes [7,8]. These hands off (or no
33 flow) intervals lead to intermittent periods with no cerebral and myocardial blood flow that deteriorate
34 the patient's condition, and compromise survival [7,9–11]. Consequently, many biomedical engineering
35 solutions have been proposed over the years to allow an AHA compliant shock/no-shock decision
36 during CPR [12]. These methods are based on adaptive filters to remove CPR artifacts. Adaptive filters
37 are needed to address the time and frequency variability of the artefact and its spectral overlap with
38 OHCA rhythms [13]. Adaptive filters use signals recorded by the defibrillator like compression depth
39 (CD) or thoracic impedance (TI) to model the artifact [14,15]. Several adaptive approaches have been
40 demonstrated including Wiener filters [16], Matching Pursuit Algorithms [17], Recursive Least Squares
41 (RLS) [18], Least Mean Squares (LMS) [19], or Kalman filters [20,21]. Once the artifact is removed the
42 ECG is analyzed using the shock/no-shock algorithms in defibrillators, or ad-hoc algorithms specially
43 designed to analyze the filtered ECG [17,19,22]. The latter have shown the highest Se/Sp values
44 by exploiting recent advances in ECG feature extraction and classical machine learning algorithms.
45 ECG features are customarily computed in time, frequency or time-frequency domains [23–26]. These
46 features have been efficiently combined using classical machine learning classification algorithms like
47 support vector machines (SVM) or random forests (RF) [22,25,26].

48 Recently deep learning approaches have proven to be superior to classical machine learning
49 algorithms in many biomedical signal applications [27,28], including arrhythmia classification based on
50 the ECG waveform [29–33]. Deep learning algorithms using convolutional neural networks (CNN)
51 are end-to-end solutions in which the algorithm learns efficient internal representations of the data
52 (features) and combines them to solve the classification task [34,35]. Deep learning algorithms have
53 already been shown to outperform classical machine learning algorithms in some OHCA applications,
54 such as detection of VF in artefact free ECG [30,36], or the detection of pulse [37]. However, deep
55 learning has not been applied to design shock/no-shock decision algorithms during CPR.

56 The objective of this study was to design the first deep learning solution to discriminate shockable
57 from nonshockable rhythms during CPR. The method comprises two stages, an adaptive RLS filter
58 to remove CPR artifacts from the ECG followed by a CNN to classify the filtered ECG. The paper is
59 organized as follows: the study dataset is detailed in section 2, section 3 describes the methodology
60 including the CNN architecture and the evaluation procedure. The results are presented in section 4,
61 discussed in section 5 and the main conclusions are presented in section 6.

62 2. Materials

63 Data were extracted from a large prospective clinical trial designed to measure CPR quality
64 during OHCA [38]. The study was conducted between March 2002 and September 2004 by the
65 emergency services of London, Stockholm and Akershus (Norway). CPR was performed using
66 prototype defibrillators based on HeartStart 4000 (Philips Medical Systems, Andover, Mass) together
67 with a sternal CPR assist pad fitted with an accelerometer (ADXL202e, AnalogDevice, Norwood, Mass).
68 The raw data for this study consisted of the ECG and TI signals acquired through the defibrillation
69 pads and the CD signal derived from accelerometer data [16]. Defibrillator data was anonymized and
70 converted to Matlab (MathWorks Inc, Natick MA) using a sampling rate of 250 Hz. The ECG had an
71 amplitude resolution of 1.031 μV per least significant bit. A notch filter and a Hampel filter were used
72 to remove powerline interferences and spiky artifacts from the ECG [37]. Finally, chest compressions
73 instants (t_k) were automatically marked using a negative peak detector with a 1 cm threshold on the
74 CD signal (see Figure 1, peak detection Th) [15].

75 The rhythms in the OHCA episodes were originally annotated by two experienced resuscitation
76 researchers/practitioners, a biomedical engineer and an anesthesiologist [38]. For the purpose of
77 this study the rhythm annotations were grouped into shockable and nonshockable. Shockable
78 rhythms comprised lethal ventricular arrhythmias, predominantly VF but also pulseless ventricular

79 tachycardia. Non-shockable rhythms included asystole (AS), the absence of electrical activity, and
 80 organized rhythms (ORG), or rhythms with visible QRS complexes. From the complete episodes
 81 15.5 sec segments were automatically extracted following these criteria: unique rhythm type in the
 82 segment and an interval of 12.5 sec with ongoing compressions followed or preceded by a 3 sec
 83 interval without compressions. The 12.5 sec interval with ongoing compressions was used to develop
 84 the shock/no-shock decision algorithm, and the 3 sec segment was used to confirm the original
 85 rhythm annotation in an artifact free ECG. All the data were visually revised (double blind process by
 86 authors UI and TE) to ensure compliance with the extraction criteria and the correctness of the rhythm
 87 annotations. The annotated dataset contained 3319 segments from 272 OHCA patients, whereof 586
 88 were shockable and 2733 (1192 AS and 1541 ORG) were nonshockable.

89 3. Methods

90 The shock/no-shock decision algorithms proposed in this study are composed of two stages.
 91 First, an adaptive RLS filter was used to remove chest compression artifacts from the ECG. Then
 92 shock/no-shock decision algorithms were designed to classify the filtered ECG using CNNs. In what
 93 follows $t = n \cdot T_s$, where $T_s = 4$ ms is the sampling period ($f_s = 250$ Hz).

94 3.1. CPR artifact suppressing filter

95 CPR artifacts were suppressed using a state-of-the-art method [26,39] based on a RLS filter
 96 designed to remove periodic interferences [40]. The CPR artifact is modelled as a quasi-periodic
 97 interference using a Fourier series truncated to N terms (harmonics). The fundamental frequency of
 98 the artifact is that of the chest compressions [19], which is assumed constant during a chest compression,
 99 but variable from compression to compression. This means that for an interval between two successive
 100 compressions at time points, t_{k-1} and t_k (see Figure 2), the frequency can be expressed as:

Figure 1. A 70 sec interval from an OHCA episode showing the ECG, CD and TI signals. Activity shows CPR followed by a pause for rhythm analysis, the delivery of a defibrillation shock (Dfb) and immediate resumption of CPR. The interval highlighted in grey corresponds to a 15.5 sec segment in the dataset. During the first 12.5 sec of the segment chest compressions were delivered (see activity in TI and CD), and in the last 3 sec there were no compressions and the ground truth rhythm (VF) for the whole segment could be annotated.

$$f_0(n) = \frac{1}{t_k - t_{k-1}} \quad t_{k-1} \leq nT_s < t_k \quad (1)$$

101 and the N -term Fourier series representation is then:

$$\hat{s}_{\text{cpr}}(n) = A(n) \sum_{\ell=1}^N a_{\ell}(n) \cos(\ell 2\pi f_0(n) T_s n) + b_{\ell}(n) \sin(\ell 2\pi f_0(n) T_s n)$$

102 where $A(n)$ is an amplitude envelope which differentiates intervals with ($A = 1$) and without
 103 compressions ($A = 0$), N is the number of harmonics in the Fourier series and $f_0(n)$ is the instantaneous
 104 chest compression frequency.

105 The RLS filter adaptively estimates the time-varying Fourier coefficients, $a_{\ell}(n)$ and $b_{\ell}(n)$, of the
 106 CPR artifact, $\hat{s}_{\text{cpr}}(n)$, by minimizing in each iteration the error between the corrupted ECG, $s_{\text{cor}}(n)$, and
 107 the estimated underlying ECG, $\hat{s}_{\text{ecg}}(n)$, at the harmonics of $f_0(n)$. The underlying ECG is estimated
 108 assuming an additive noise model, so $\hat{s}_{\text{ecg}}(n) = s_{\text{cor}}(n) - \hat{s}_{\text{cpr}}(n)$. A detailed description of the RLS
 109 filter equations is available in [39], and the values recommended there to suppress CPR artefacts were
 110 used in this study, that is, $N = 4$ and a forgetting factor of $\lambda = 0.999$ [39].

111 3.2. Shock/no-shock decision algorithms

112 The shock/no-shock algorithms trained and evaluated in this study comprise algorithms based
 113 on CNNs (core methods of the paper), and a state of the art algorithm based on classical machine
 114 learning techniques used as a baseline model for comparison. In both cases, the algorithms were
 115 designed to analyse the filtered ECG in the interval from 3-12 sec during compressions (see analysis
 116 interval in Figure 2). That is, the algorithms use 9 sec of the filtered ECG for a decision, excluding
 117 the initial 3 sec to avoid RLS filtering transients [39]. The analysis interval was further divided into

Figure 2. A 15.5 sec segment from the study dataset corresponding to a patient in an organized rhythm is shown. In the initial 3 sec interval without compressions three QRS complexes are visible, and the nonshockable rhythm annotation was confirmed. The following 12.5 sec are corrupted by CPR artifacts (top panel) that conceal the underlying rhythm. The output of the adaptive filter, $\hat{s}_{\text{ecg}}(n)$, reveals the underlying rhythm during chest compressions. CPR activity and the chest compression instants (t_k) can be observed in the CD signal (bottom).

118 three non-overlapping analysis windows of 3 sec (see Figure 2) and the shock/no-shock decision
 119 was obtained as the majority vote. The combination of consecutive analysis windows is a typical
 120 design practice in shock/no-shock decision algorithms for defibrillators [22,41], because it increases the
 121 reliability of the diagnosis by avoiding the effects of transient lower quality signal intervals, rhythm
 122 changes or filtering misadjustments.

123 3.2.1. Algorithm based on CNNs

124 Figure 3 shows the architecture of the shock/no-shock decision algorithms based on CNNs. First
 125 the 3 sec window of the filtered ECG is downsampled to 125 Hz, resulting in a 1-D signal of $N=375$
 126 samples, $\hat{s}_{\text{ecg}}(n)$. Then the CNN is composed of three convolutional blocks to extract the high level
 127 descriptors of the ECG, and two fully connected layers for classification. The b -th convolutional block
 128 consists of a convolutional layer with J_b filters of width I_b , followed by a batch normalization layer, a
 129 rectified linear unit (ReLU), a max-pooling layer ($K=3$) and a dropout layer.

130 Let us denote by $s_{b-1}(n, m)$ the output of block $b - 1$ (input to block b), where n is the time index
 131 and m the filter index. At the input of the first block we have $s_0(n, 1) = \hat{s}_{\text{ecg}}(n)$. The output of the
 132 Conv-1D layer at block b can be expressed as:

$$c_b(n, m) = f\left(b_m + \sum_{\ell=1}^{J_{b-1}} \sum_{i=1}^{I_b} \omega_{\ell,i}^m s_{b-1}(n+i-1, \ell)\right) \quad (2)$$

133 where $f(x) = \max(x, 0)$ is the ReLU activation function that makes the network non-linear. The
 134 max-pooling layer selects the largest sample in blocks of K samples along the time index n to give the
 135 output of block b :

$$s_b(n, m) = \max\{c_b(k, m)\}_{k=(n-1)\cdot K, \dots, n\cdot K} \quad (3)$$

136 Padding was applied before the convolutional and the max-pooling layers, so the only reduction of
 137 the dimensionality occurs at the max-pooling layers ($K = 3$). This means that the dimensions of the
 138 outputs at blocks $b = 1, 2, 3$ where $(125, J_1)$, $(41, J_2)$ and $(13, J_3)$, respectively and that the number of
 139 learnable parameters (ω, b) at block b where $J_b \times I_b + J_b$.

140 The dropout layer at the end of each block has a regularization effect, and is used only during
 141 training to avoid overfitting. It temporarily deactivates a randomly selected proportion of the

Figure 3. Architecture of the CNN-based shock/no-shock algorithm. It comprises two main stages: a CNN composed of three identical blocks and a classification stage based on two fully connected and a softmax layer.

142 network's tunable parameters, and has been shown to improve performance by providing noisy inputs
 143 to the fully connected layers that help avoid overfitting [42].

144 The classification stage takes as input the flattened $13 \times J_3$ features and fed them into two
 145 fully-connected layers. The first one is composed by 10 hidden units whereas the second one uses
 146 2 neurons for the 2-class classification task. In the second fully-connected layer a softmax function
 147 is used to convert the output of the last two neurons into two values in the [0,1] range that can be
 148 interpreted as the likelihood that the 3 sec window is shockable (p_{Sh}) or nonshockable (p_{NSh}).

149 The weights and biases of every layer were optimized using stochastic gradient descent with a
 150 momentum of 0.8. The initial learning rate was fixed to 0.02 and it was reduced by a factor of 0.8 at
 151 every epoch. The training data were fed into the CNN in batches of 256, and 20 epochs were used to
 152 train the networks [43]. During training data was augmented by splitting each 9 sec training segment
 153 into overlapping 3 sec windows with a linearly spaced start between 0 sec and 6 sec of the segment. To
 154 address class imbalance the augmented number of windows per segment during training was fixed to
 155 100 for shockable and 40 for nonshockable rhythms, respectively. The binary cross entropy was used
 156 as loss function during network optimization (training):

$$L = \sum_i y_i \ln(p_{Sh_i}) + (1 - y_i) \ln(1 - p_{Sh_i}) \quad (4)$$

157 where $y_i = \{0 : NSh, 1 : Sh\}$ corresponds to the rhythm label of 3 sec training window i .

158 3.2.2. Classical machine learning shock/no-shock decision algorithm for baseline comparison

159 The baseline machine learning shock/no-shock algorithm is a state of the art solution described
 160 in [25]. In short, the algorithm is based on multiresolution ECG analysis using the Stationary Wavelet
 161 Transform (SWT) for feature extraction, followed by a random forest (RF) classifier. The SWT
 162 decomposes the 3 sec window into 7 sub-bands using a daubechies-2 mother wavelet, and the denoised
 163 ECG is reconstructed using detail coefficients d_3 to d_7 , i.e. an analysis band of 0.98 – 31.25 Hz. The
 164 denoised ECG, $s_{den}(n)$, and the detail coefficients d_3 - d_7 were used to obtain twenty five ECG features,
 165 selected using recursive feature elimination from a set of over 200 features (consult [25] for the details).
 166 The most relevant features were classical VF detection features like VFleak or x_4 [22,44] computed from
 167 s_{den} , and a rich set of features obtained from the detail coefficients $\{d_i\}_{i=3,\dots,7}$, such as: sample entropy
 168 ($SampEn(d_i)$), the mean and standard deviation of the absolute value of the signal ($\overline{|d_i|}$, $\sigma(|d_i|)$) and
 169 its slope ($\overline{|\Delta d_i|}$, $\sigma(|\Delta d_i|)$), and the Hjorth mobility ($Hmb(d_i)$) and complexity ($Hmc(d_i)$) indices [45]. A
 170 detailed description of the algorithm is found in [25], with a detailed bibliography for the computation
 171 of the features.

172 The parameters of the RF classifier were fixed to those recommended in [25], that is $B=500$ trees, 5
 173 predictors per split (standard in RF), and the minimum observations per leaf to 3 (to avoid growing
 174 excessively deep or overfit trees). To avoid class imbalance uniform priors were assigned and a cost
 175 function was introduced to penalize false shock classifications with a factor of 2.5 (similar to the
 176 shock/no-shock augmentation factor used in the CNN).

177 3.3. Evaluation

178 All the classification algorithms were trained/tested using 5-fold cross validation (CV). Folds
 179 were partitioned patient-wise to avoid training/test data leakage, and in a quasi-stratified way by
 180 ensuring that the shock/no-shock prevalences in all folds were at least 80% those of the whole dataset.
 181 The performance of the method was evaluated using the standard metrics for binary classification
 182 problems, taking the shockable class as positive and the nonshockable class as negative. For a 2x2
 183 confusion matrix with true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives
 184 (FN) the performance metrics were:

$$Se = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad PPV = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (5)$$

$$Sp = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad NPV = \frac{TN}{TN + FN} \quad (6)$$

$$Acc = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FN+TN+FP} \quad BAC = \frac{1}{2}(Se + Sp) \quad (7)$$

185 The BAC was used as target performance metric to ensure both shockable and nonshockable
 186 rhythms were accurately identified (as recommended by the AHA) despite the large class imbalance in
 187 the data.

188 4. Results

189 4.1. Parameters of the CNN architecture

190 The effect of changing the main parameters of the CNN architecture was first studied taking the
 191 BAC as target performance metric (see Figure 4). Three parameters were studied : the number of blocks
 192 (B), the size of the filters (I), and the number of filters ($\mathbf{L} = (J_1, \dots, J_B)$). Four filter configurations were
 193 studied with decreasing number of filters (from dense to sparse): $\mathbf{L}_4=(40,30,20,10)$, $\mathbf{L}_3=(32,24,16,8)$,
 194 $\mathbf{L}_2=(24,18,12,6)$ and $\mathbf{L}_1=(16,12,8,4)$. The numbers in parentheses indicate the amount of filters from
 195 block 1 to block 4, so for an architecture with 3 blocks and \mathbf{L}_2 the number of filters would be (24,18,12).

196 The results of the analysis are shown in Figure 4, with the median BAC computed over the
 197 5-fold CV partitions. The best classification results were obtained for 3 blocks. Adding a fourth block
 198 increases the complexity (number of trainable parameters) and slightly decreases the performance.
 199 Using only 2 blocks resulted in a large decrease in performance (over 1-point in BAC), or an overly
 200 simplistic model. The best results for a CNN with 3 blocks were obtained with a filter width of $I = 16$,
 201 and a filter configuration of $\mathbf{L} = (32, 24, 16)$. This was the CNN configuration adopted for the rest of
 202 the analyses.

Figure 4. Performance of the CNN architecture for the configurable parameters of the network: the number of blocks (B), the filter size (I), and the filter configuration (\mathbf{L}). The left panel shows the effect of the filter size for networks with $\mathbf{L}_4 = (32, 24, 16, 8)$ filters. The right panel shows the effect of the filter configurations from dense (\mathbf{L}_4) to sparse (\mathbf{L}_1) for $I = 16$.

203 4.2. Comparison with the baseline machine learning model

204 The shock/no-shock decision algorithms using CNNs and the classical machine learning model
 205 were compared. Table 1 shows the results for all the performance metrics. The accuracies were
 206 compared using McNemar’s test in all 5-fold CV partitions, and the results were considered significant
 207 at the 95% level. The CNN model was significantly more accurate (median $p < 0.05$) than the baseline
 208 model. As shown in Table 1 the CNN model designed for 9 sec improves the best baseline models
 209 in 0.6-points in BAC and Acc, and in both cases the algorithms presented balanced Se/Sp values
 210 because they were trained to avoid class imbalance. The predictivity is higher for the CNN solution,
 211 but the differences are only large for shockable rhythms (PPV) because shockable rhythms have a
 212 much lower prevalence in the dataset (1 to 5). The table shows the results for the 3 sec windows (where
 213 CNN outperforms the baseline model), but also for the combination of three consecutive analyses
 214 (9 sec). For short windows the algorithms do not meet the minimum 95% value recommended by
 215 the AHA for artifact free ECG, but combining diagnoses with a majority vote criterion considerably
 216 improves performance and brings both the CNN solution and the baseline algorithm above AHA
 217 specifications. The table also shows the shock/no-shock decision performance when the two subgroups
 218 of nonshockable rhythms were evaluated separately, AS and ORG rhythms. The results show that
 219 no-shock decisions were more inaccurate when the underlying rhythm was asystole. For 9 sec segments
 220 the CNN architecture yielded results slightly above the AHA’s 95% Sp goal for AS, but the baseline
 model was marginally below.

Table 1. Performance metrics for the CNN and the baseline models. The results are shown as median and 90% confidence interval (CI).

	3 sec		9 sec	
	CNN	baseline	CNN	baseline
Se	93.2 (92.2-94.0)	93.1 (92.6-93.6)	95.8 (94.6-96.8)	95.2 (94.7-95.7)
Sp	94.5 (94.1-94.9)	94.1 (93.9-94.3)	96.1 (95.8-96.5)	95.6 (95.2-95.9)
AS	93.1 (92.6-93.7)	92.5 (92.2-92.8)	95.4 (94.9-96.0)	94.5 (94.1-95.0)
ORG	95.6 (95.1-96.0)	95.3 (95.1-95.6)	96.8 (96.2-97.4)	96.4 (96.0-96.8)
BAC	93.8 (93.4-94.3)	93.6 (93.3-93.9)	96.0 (95.5-96.5)	95.4 (95.0-95.7)
Acc	94.3 (94.0-94.6)	93.9 (93.7-94.1)	96.1 (95.7-96.4)	95.5 (95.2-95.8)
PPV	78.5 (77.2-79.6)	77.2 (76.5-77.7)	84.3 (82.8-85.6)	82.2 (81.0-83.2)
NPV	98.5 (98.3-98.7)	98.5 (98.3-98.6)	99.1 (98.8-99.3)	98.9 (98.8-99.1)

221

222 4.3. Effect of the ECG corruption level on classification

223 CPR artifacts during chest compressions present very different noise levels in the ECG depending
 224 on variables like the position of the hands relative to the pads and cables, pad placement, or
 225 environmental conditions [46,47]. These variables are difficult to control in a pre-hospital setting,
 226 but it is important to know what the observed corruption levels are, and how these corruption levels
 227 affect the shock/no-shock decisions. To estimate the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) we assumed that the
 228 underlying ECG was stationary over the 15 sec segments, and thus estimated the power of the clean
 229 signal (P_{ecg}) in the 3 sec interval without artifacts used to confirm the rhythm annotations. Then, we
 230 used the CPR artifact estimated by the RLS filter to compute the power of the noise (P_{cpr}), and to
 231 obtain the SNR as:

$$\text{SNR} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_{\text{ecg}}}{P_{\text{cpr}}} \right) \quad (\text{dB}) \quad (8)$$

232 The noise levels were divided into bins from very large corruption levels (SNR < -18 dB) to very
 233 low corruption levels (SNR > 6 dB). The distributions of noise levels and the classification results for

234 the different noise conditions are shown in Figure 5 for shockable (left) and nonshockable (right)
 235 rhythms. As expected the classification results improve as noise conditions improve, but noise affects
 236 the classification of shockable and nonshockable rhythms very differently. Nonshockable rhythms are
 237 detected with high specificity even in very noisy conditions, and the confidence in a nonshockable
 238 diagnosis (NPV) is high because the prevalence of nonshockable rhythms is 5/1 that of shockable
 239 rhythms. The sensitivity for shockable rhythms improves considerably as noise conditions improve,
 240 and was above the 90% value recommended by the AHA for SNR > -10 dB. However, the confidence
 241 on a shock diagnosis (PPV) is good only for SNR > -6 dB because of the lower prevalence of shockable
 242 rhythms. The SNR was significantly higher for nonshockable than for shockable rhythms ($p < 0.001$,
 243 Mann-Whitney U test), and in approximately 15% of shockable and nonshockable cases the noise level
 244 was negligible (SNR > 25 dB, see Figure 5). Although noise levels were lower in nonshockable rhythms,
 245 a high specificity was obtained regardless of the noise conditions. Even for the very noisy segments
 246 (SNR < -12 dB) the specificity was above 94%.

Figure 5. Median values of the performance metrics for shockable and nonshockable rhythms as a function of the SNR. The SNR levels were divided into 6 dB bins for the analysis from high (<-18 dB) to low (>6 dB) corruption levels. The lower panels show the SNR distributions for shockable (left) and nonshockable rhythms (right).

247 4.4. Feature extraction using CNNs

248 For these experiments we used the 10 features at the output of the first fully connected layer as the
 249 features learned by our solution, these features will be named $\{f_i\}_{i=1,\dots,10}$. To evaluate feature extraction

250 two experiments were conducted [36], and the results were compared to those obtained using the
 251 multiresolution features based on the SWT in the baseline model [25]. First, a dimensionality reduction
 252 experiment was conducted by projecting the feature space into a 2-D space using the t-distributed
 253 stochastic neighbour embedding (t-SNE) algorithm [48]. The results were visually assessed, and are
 254 shown in Figure 6 for the f_i features and the handcrafted multiresolution features. The classes are
 255 shown in colors and the nonshockable rhythms are further divided into AS and ORG. As shown in the
 256 figure the CNN features produce better defined clusters than the handcrafted features in the 2D space.
 257 To numerically evaluate how the classes were clustered the Davies-Boudin index (DBi) was computed
 258 to measure the separability of the clusters [49]. The experiment was repeated on 500 bootstrap replicas
 259 and the mean (standard deviation) BDi for the CNN and the handcrafted features were 2.28 (0.06) and
 260 4.95 (0.17), respectively ($p < 0.05$, for the paired t-test) [50]. That is, the features learned by the CNN
 261 architecture resulted in a more efficient clustering of the classes, and thus to a better separability.

Figure 6. 2D map representation of the separability of the classes for the features learned by the CNN (left) and the handcrafted features (right). These maps were obtained using the t-SNE algorithm.

Table 2. Mean (standard deviation) of the AUCs for the CNN features and the handcrafted features obtained using 100 bootstrap replicas of the data.

CNN		Machine learning	
Feature	AUC	Feature	AUC
f_6	97.2 (1.1)	SampEn(d_3)	90.6 (2.0)
f_{10}	96.4 (1.6)	$\sigma(\Delta d_4)$	90.3 (1.7)
f_1	95.2 (2.6)	$\sigma(d_4)$	87.7 (1.8)
f_5	94.8 (2.3)	$\sigma(d_3)$	86.2 (2.3)
f_9	90.7 (3.7)	VFLeak	85.9 (2.7)
f_3	81.2 (11.1)	SampEn(d_4)	84.8 (2.4)
f_8	75.2 (10.6)	$ \Delta d_3 $	84.6 (2.8)
f_4	73.9 (8.6)	x4	82.5 (3.6)
f_7	66.9 (6.2)	$\sigma(s_{den})$	82.4 (2.0)
f_2	59.3 (17.1)	SampEn(d_6)	80.6 (2.7)

262 Second, the discriminative power of each feature was computed using the area under the receiver
 263 characteristics curve (AUC). The results were obtained over 500 bootstrap replicas to statistically
 264 characterize the AUCs and compare the AUC distributions for each feature (paired t-test). The results
 265 are shown in Table 2, which shows that the four top most discriminative features (f_6 , f_{10} , f_1 and f_5)

266 had significantly higher AUCs ($p < 0.05$) than any of the handcrafted features. These results confirm
 267 the ability of the CNN to extract high quality discriminative features hidden in the signals.

268 4.5. Analysis of classification errors

269 To conclude the analyses, the classification errors for the CNN based algorithm were identified.
 270 Some typical patterns leading to errors are shown in Figure 7. Most of the false positives are

Figure 7. Examples of classification errors. Segments corresponding to nonshockable rhythms (OR panel a and AS panel b) are shown in blue, whereas segments corresponding to shockable rhythms (panels c and d) are shown in orange.

271 caused by the inability of the RLS filter to properly remove artifacts, leading to very disorganized
272 filtering residuals that resemble a VF. Most false negatives occur at low SNR levels with compression
273 rates around 100 min^{-1} . In these cases the filtered ECG still shows an organized activity locked to
274 the compression frequency, incompatible with fast ventricular arrhythmia and thus classified as
275 non-shockable. Interestingly, these errors can be related to the clustering analysis of section 4.4. Most
276 errors cluster around borderline AS/VF rhythms which appear in the center-left region of the 2D t-SNE
277 map (Figure 6), and ORG/VF rhythms in a much lower proportion in the top-center.

278 5. Discussion

279 This is, to the best of our knowledge, the first study that uses deep neural network models to
280 discriminate between shockable and nonshockable rhythms during CPR. Our algorithm consists of
281 an adaptive RLS filter to remove CPR artifacts followed by a CNN to classify the filtered ECG. The
282 algorithm designed for 9 sec improves the performance of the classical machine learning algorithms
283 by 0.6 points in BAC and Acc. This improvement is large considering that the best classical machine
284 learning algorithms had accuracies over 95% and that they are based on more than 20 years of expert
285 knowledge on ECG feature engineering.

286 One of the advantages of deep learning solutions is the capacity of the algorithms to learn
287 discriminative features exploiting all information hidden in the ECG. This avoids the time-consuming
288 feature extraction processes and, most importantly, improves the quality of the extracted features. The
289 latter is well reflected by the AUCs on Table 2. Four of the ten features extracted by the deep learning
290 architecture show a higher discrimination capacity than $\text{SampEn}(d_3)$, which is the best handcrafted
291 feature for shock/no-shock decisions during CPR in the available literature [25,26].

292 Two factors were key to improve the performance of the CNN based methods from our
293 preliminary results communicated previously in [51]. First, we designed and optimized the parameters
294 of the CNN obtaining a better model for classification. Second, we increased the size of the database
295 adding 1186 new annotated samples (a 55% increase in dataset size). These led to 0.5-points and
296 0.3-points increases in BAC and Acc respectively, of which 0.4-points and 0.1-points are attributable
297 to the larger dataset. The performance of deep learning solutions improves as they are exposed to more
298 data, whereas the accuracy of classical machine learning algorithms stagnate past a given sample size.
299 Our model overfits when more than 3 CNN blocks are used (Figure 4) since from then on the number
300 of trainable parameters is too large for the size of the available dataset. Adding more data would
301 help to develop deeper networks and thus to the extraction of more sophisticated features. There is
302 therefore room to improve the deep learning models for rhythm analysis during CPR, as more and
303 more data is recorded every day and made available in centralized repositories. In research on OHCA,
304 the Resuscitation Outcome Consortium (ROC) network provides the largest OHCA data repository,
305 which includes recordings of eleven regional clinical centers. However, labeled OHCA data are scarce,
306 and obtaining quality controlled rhythm annotations from clinicians is expensive and time consuming.
307 As an alternative, semi-supervised learning could be an efficient way to augment our training data
308 and obtain better deep learning models in the future.

309 As Figure 6 shows, CNN features provide more separate clusters than the handcrafted features
310 for the shock/no-shock classes. Moreover, the deep learning model shows a quite high separability
311 between the features corresponding to AS, OR and shockable rhythms. Therefore, we foresee that CNN
312 models could improve the accuracy of classical machine learning-based multiclass rhythm classifiers.
313 These classifiers have been demonstrated for clean [24,52] and artefacted ECGs [25], and are multilabel
314 classification algorithms that classify the ECG into the 5 OHCA rhythm types. These algorithms are
315 important for research to analyze large sets of OHCA data [24], and could also help clinicians during
316 OHCA treatment as clinical support tools. The best OHCA multiclass algorithms have unweighted
317 mean sensitivities of 78% for clean ECG [24], and of 72% if the analysis is done during CPR [25]. There
318 is therefore margin for improvement using methods based on deep learning if sufficiently large quality
319 controlled annotated datasets become available.

320 6. Conclusions

321 This paper introduces the first shock/no-shock decision algorithm during CPR based on deep
 322 learning methods. Our solution improves the accuracy of the best classical machine learning models
 323 based on handcrafted features, and is able to give a shock/no-shock diagnosis compliant with AHA
 324 recommendations for shockable and nonshockable rhythms. Moreover, deep learning algorithms have
 325 room for improvement if larger annotated datasets become available allowing the design of deeper
 326 networks. This may lead to the first practical solutions for rhythm analysis during CPR, eliminating
 327 the no-flow intervals for rhythm analysis and contributing to improve OHCA survival rates.

328 **Author Contributions:** Conceptualization, J.K.J., L.W., I.I., U.I., E.A. and T.E.; methodology, I.I. and U.I.; software,
 329 I.I.; validation, U.I.; formal analysis, I.I. and U.I.; investigation, I.I., U.I., E.A., T.E., J.K.J. and L.W.; resources, J.K.J.
 330 and L.W.; data curation, U.I., E.A., T.E. and I.I.; writing—original draft preparation, I.I. and U.I.; writing—review
 331 and editing, I.I., U.I., E.A., T.E., J.K.J. and L.W.; visualization, I.I. and U.I.; supervision, U.I. and E.A.; project
 332 administration, U.I. and E.A.; funding acquisition, U.I. and E.A. All authors have read and agreed to the published
 333 version of the manuscript.

334 **Funding:** This work was supported by the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovacion y Universidades through
 335 grant RTI2018-101475-BI00, jointly with the Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional (FEDER), and by the Basque
 336 Government through grants IT1229-19 and PRE-2019-2-0066.

337 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

338 Abbreviations

339 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

340

CPR	cardiopulmonary resuscitation
CNN	convolutional neural network
RLS	recursive least squares
OHCA	out of hospital cardiac arrest
ECG	electrocardiogram
VF	ventricular fibrillation
VT	ventricular tachycardia
ORG	organized
AS	asystole
AHA	American Heart Association
CD	compression depth
TI	thoracic impedance
LMS	least mean squares
SVM	support vector machine
RF	random forest
341 SWT	stationary wavelet transform
TP	true positive
TN	true negative
FP	false positive
FN	false negative
Se	sensitivity
Sp	specificity
Acc	accuracy
BAC	balanced accuracy
PPV	positive predictive value
NPV	negative predictive value
SNR	signal-to-noise ratio
t-SNE	t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding
DBi	Davies-Bouldin index
AUC	area under the receiver characteristics curve
ROC	Resuscitation Outcome Consortium

342 **References**

- 343 1. Berdowski, J.; Berg, R.A.; Tijssen, J.G.; Koster, R.W. Global incidences of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest and
344 survival rates: systematic review of 67 prospective studies. *Resuscitation* **2010**, *81*, 1479–1487.
- 345 2. Daya, M.R.; Schmicker, R.H.; Zive, D.M.; Rea, T.D.; Nichol, G.; Buick, J.E.; Brooks, S.; Christenson, J.;
346 MacPhee, R.; Craig, A.; others. Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest survival improving over time: results from
347 the Resuscitation Outcomes Consortium (ROC). *Resuscitation* **2015**, *91*, 108–115.
- 348 3. Perkins, G.; Handley, A.; Koster, R.; Castrén, M.; Smyth, M.; Olasveengen, T.; Monsieurs, K.; Raffay, V.;
349 Gärsner, J.; Wenzel, V.; others. European Resuscitation Council Guidelines for Resuscitation 2015: Section
350 2. Adult basic life support and automated external defibrillation. *Resuscitation* **2015**, *95*, 81–99.
- 351 4. Takata, T.S.; Page, R.L.; Joglar, J.A. Automated external defibrillators: technical considerations and clinical
352 promise. *Annals of internal medicine* **2001**, *135*, 990–998.
- 353 5. Kerber, R.E.; Becker, L.B.; Bourland, J.D.; Cummins, R.O.; Hallstrom, A.P.; Michos, M.B.; Nichol, G.; Ornato,
354 J.P.; Thies, W.H.; White, R.D.; others. Automatic external defibrillators for public access defibrillation:
355 recommendations for specifying and reporting arrhythmia analysis algorithm performance, incorporating
356 new waveforms, and enhancing safety: a statement for health professionals from the American Heart
357 Association Task Force on Automatic External Defibrillation, Subcommittee on AED Safety and Efficacy.
358 *Circulation* **1997**, *95*, 1677–1682.
- 359 6. Snyder, D.; Morgan, C. Wide variation in cardiopulmonary resuscitation interruption intervals among
360 commercially available automated external defibrillators may affect survival despite high defibrillation
361 efficacy. *Critical care medicine* **2004**, *32*, S421–S424.
- 362 7. Van Alem, A.P.; Sanou, B.T.; Koster, R.W. Interruption of cardiopulmonary resuscitation with the use of
363 the automated external defibrillator in out-of-hospital cardiac arrest. *Annals of emergency medicine* **2003**,
364 *42*, 449–457.
- 365 8. Li, Y.; Tang, W. Techniques for artefact filtering from chest compression corrupted ECG signals: good, but
366 not enough. *Resuscitation* **2009**, *80*, 1219–1220.
- 367 9. Sato, Y.; Weil, M.H.; Sun, S.; Tang, W.; Xie, J.; Noc, M.; Bisera, J. Adverse effects of interrupting precordial
368 compression during cardiopulmonary resuscitation. *Critical care medicine* **1997**, *25*, 733–736.
- 369 10. Eftestøl, T.; Sunde, K.; Steen, P.A. Effects of interrupting precordial compressions on the calculated
370 probability of defibrillation success during out-of-hospital cardiac arrest. *Circulation* **2002**, *105*, 2270–2273.
- 371 11. Edelson, D.P.; Abella, B.S.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Wik, L.; Myklebust, H.; Barry, A.M.; Merchant, R.M.; Hoek,
372 T.L.V.; Steen, P.A.; Becker, L.B. Effects of compression depth and pre-shock pauses predict defibrillation
373 failure during cardiac arrest. *Resuscitation* **2006**, *71*, 137–145.
- 374 12. Ruiz de Gauna, S.; Irusta, U.; Ruiz, J.; Ayala, U.; Aramendi, E.; Eftestøl, T. Rhythm analysis during
375 cardiopulmonary resuscitation: past, present, and future. *BioMed research international* **2014**, *2014*.
- 376 13. Werther, T.; Klotz, A.; Granegger, M.; Baubin, M.; Feichtinger, H.G.; Amann, A.; Gilly, H. Strong corruption
377 of electrocardiograms caused by cardiopulmonary resuscitation reduces efficiency of two-channel methods
378 for removing motion artefacts in non-shockable rhythms. *Resuscitation* **2009**, *80*, 1301–1307.
- 379 14. Irusta, U.; Ruiz, J. An algorithm to discriminate supraventricular from ventricular tachycardia in automated
380 external defibrillators valid for adult and paediatric patients. *Resuscitation* **2009**, *80*, 1229–1233.
- 381 15. Ayala, U.; Eftestøl, T.; Alonso, E.; Irusta, U.; Aramendi, E.; Wali, S.; Kramer-Johansen, J. Automatic detection
382 of chest compressions for the assessment of CPR-quality parameters. *Resuscitation* **2014**, *85*, 957–963.
- 383 16. Aase, S.O.; Eftestøl, T.; Husoy, J.; Sunde, K.; Steen, P.A. CPR artifact removal from human ECG using
384 optimal multichannel filtering. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **2000**, *47*, 1440–1449.
- 385 17. Eilevstjønn, J.; Eftestøl, T.; Aase, S.O.; Myklebust, H.; Husøy, J.H.; Steen, P.A. Feasibility of shock
386 advice analysis during CPR through removal of CPR artefacts from the human ECG. *Resuscitation* **2004**,
387 *61*, 131–141.
- 388 18. Berger, R.D.; Palazzolo, J.; Halperin, H. Rhythm discrimination during uninterrupted CPR using motion
389 artifact reduction system. *Resuscitation* **2007**, *75*, 145–152.
- 390 19. Irusta, U.; Ruiz, J.; de Gauna, S.R.; Eftestøl, T.; Kramer-Johansen, J. A least mean-square filter for the
391 estimation of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation artifact based on the frequency of the compressions. *IEEE*
392 *Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **2009**, *56*, 1052–1062.

- 393 20. Rheinberger, K.; Steinberger, T.; Unterkofler, K.; Baubin, M.; Klotz, A.; Amann, A. Removal of CPR artifacts
394 from the ventricular fibrillation ECG by adaptive regression on lagged reference signals. *IEEE Transactions*
395 *on Biomedical Engineering* **2007**, *55*, 130–137.
- 396 21. Ruiz, J.; Irusta, U.; de Gauna, S.R.; Eftestøl, T. Cardiopulmonary resuscitation artefact suppression using
397 a Kalman filter and the frequency of chest compressions as the reference signal. *Resuscitation* **2010**,
398 *81*, 1087–1094.
- 399 22. Ayala, U.; Irusta, U.; Ruiz, J.; Eftestøl, T.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Alonso-Atienza, F.; Alonso, E.;
400 González-Otero, D. A reliable method for rhythm analysis during cardiopulmonary resuscitation. *BioMed*
401 *research international* **2014**, 2014.
- 402 23. Figuera, C.; Irusta, U.; Morgado, E.; Aramendi, E.; Ayala, U.; Wik, L.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Eftestøl, T.;
403 Alonso-Atienza, F. Machine learning techniques for the detection of shockable rhythms in automated
404 external defibrillators. *PloS one* **2016**, *11*.
- 405 24. Rad, A.B.; Eftestøl, T.; Engan, K.; Irusta, U.; Kvaløy, J.T.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Wik, L.; Katsaggelos, A.K.
406 ECG-based classification of resuscitation cardiac rhythms for retrospective data analysis. *IEEE Transactions*
407 *on Biomedical Engineering* **2017**, *64*, 2411–2418.
- 408 25. Isasi, I.; Irusta, U.; Rad, A.B.; Aramendi, E.; Zabihi, M.; Eftestøl, T.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Wik, L.
409 Automatic Cardiac Rhythm Classification With Concurrent Manual Chest Compressions. *IEEE Access* **2019**,
410 *7*, 115147–115159.
- 411 26. Isasi, I.; Irusta, U.; Elola, A.; Aramendi, E.; Ayala, U.; Alonso, E.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Eftestøl, T. A machine
412 learning shock decision algorithm for use during piston-driven chest compressions. *IEEE Transactions on*
413 *Biomedical Engineering* **2018**, *66*, 1752–1760.
- 414 27. Rim, B.; Sung, N.J.; Min, S.; Hong, M. Deep Learning in Physiological Signal Data: A Survey. *Sensors* **2020**,
415 *20*, 969.
- 416 28. Hong, S.; Zhou, Y.; Shang, J.; Xiao, C.; Sun, J. Opportunities and Challenges in Deep Learning Methods on
417 Electrocardiogram Data: A Systematic Review. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2001.01550* **2019**.
- 418 29. Kiranyaz, S.; Ince, T.; Gabbouj, M. Real-time patient-specific ECG classification by 1-D convolutional
419 neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* **2015**, *63*, 664–675.
- 420 30. Acharya, U.R.; Fujita, H.; Lih, O.S.; Hagiwara, Y.; Tan, J.H.; Adam, M. Automated detection of arrhythmias
421 using different intervals of tachycardia ECG segments with convolutional neural network. *Information*
422 *sciences* **2017**, *405*, 81–90.
- 423 31. Al Rahhal, M.M.; Bazi, Y.; Al Zuair, M.; Othman, E.; BenJdira, B. Convolutional neural networks for
424 electrocardiogram classification. *Journal of Medical and Biological Engineering* **2018**, *38*, 1014–1025.
- 425 32. Xia, Y.; Wulan, N.; Wang, K.; Zhang, H. Detecting atrial fibrillation by deep convolutional neural networks.
426 *Computers in biology and medicine* **2018**, *93*, 84–92.
- 427 33. Hannun, A.Y.; Rajpurkar, P.; Haghpanahi, M.; Tison, G.H.; Bourn, C.; Turakhia, M.P.; Ng, A.Y.
428 Cardiologist-level arrhythmia detection and classification in ambulatory electrocardiograms using a
429 deep neural network. *Nature medicine* **2019**, *25*, 65.
- 430 34. Pourbabaee, B.; Roshtkhari, M.J.; Khorasani, K. Deep convolutional neural networks and learning ECG
431 features for screening paroxysmal atrial fibrillation patients. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and*
432 *Cybernetics: Systems* **2018**, *48*, 2095–2104.
- 433 35. Andreotti, F.; Carr, O.; Pimentel, M.A.; Mahdi, A.; De Vos, M. Comparing feature-based classifiers and
434 convolutional neural networks to detect arrhythmia from short segments of ECG. 2017 Computing in
435 Cardiology (CinC). IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–4.
- 436 36. Picon, A.; Irusta, U.; Álvarez-Gila, A.; Aramendi, E.; Alonso-Atienza, F.; Figuera, C.; Ayala, U.; Garrote, E.;
437 Wik, L.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; others. Mixed convolutional and long short-term memory network for the
438 detection of lethal ventricular arrhythmia. *PloS one* **2019**, *14*.
- 439 37. Elola, A.; Aramendi, E.; Irusta, U.; Picón, A.; Alonso, E.; Owens, P.; Idris, A. Deep neural networks for
440 ECG-based pulse detection during out-of-hospital cardiac arrest. *Entropy* **2019**, *21*, 305.
- 441 38. Wik, L.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Myklebust, H.; Sørebo, H.; Svensson, L.; Fellows, B.; Steen, P.A. Quality of
442 cardiopulmonary resuscitation during out-of-hospital cardiac arrest. *Jama* **2005**, *293*, 299–304.
- 443 39. Isasi, I.; Irusta, U.; Aramendi, E.; Ayala, U.; Alonso, E.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Eftestøl, T. A multistage
444 algorithm for ECG rhythm analysis during piston-driven mechanical chest compressions. *IEEE Transactions*
445 *on Biomedical Engineering* **2018**, *66*, 263–272.

- 446 40. Xiao, Y.; Ma, L.; Ward, R.K. Fast RLS Fourier analyzers capable of accommodating frequency mismatch.
447 *Signal Processing* **2007**, *87*, 2197–2212.
- 448 41. Atkins, D.L.; Scott, W.A.; Blaufox, A.D.; Law, I.H.; Dick II, M.; Geheb, F.; Sobh, J.; Brewer, J.E. Sensitivity and
449 specificity of an automated external defibrillator algorithm designed for pediatric patients. *Resuscitation*
450 **2008**, *76*, 168–174.
- 451 42. Srivastava, N.; Hinton, G.; Krizhevsky, A.; Sutskever, I.; Salakhutdinov, R. Dropout: a simple way to
452 prevent neural networks from overfitting. *The journal of machine learning research* **2014**, *15*, 1929–1958.
- 453 43. Sutskever, I.; Martens, J.; Dahl, G.; Hinton, G. On the importance of initialization and momentum in deep
454 learning. International conference on machine learning, 2013, pp. 1139–1147.
- 455 44. Kuo, S. Computer detection of ventricular fibrillation. *Proc. of Computers in Cardiology, IEEE Computer*
456 *Society* **1978**, pp. 347–349.
- 457 45. Gonzalez, L.; Walker, K.; Challa, S.; Bent, B. Monitoring a skipped heartbeat: a real-time premature
458 ventricular contraction (pvc) monitor. 2016 IEEE Virtual Conference on Applications of Commercial
459 Sensors (VCACS). IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–7.
- 460 46. Langhelle, A.; Eftestøl, T.; Myklebust, H.; Eriksen, M.; Holten, B.T.; Steen, P.A. Reducing CPR artefacts in
461 ventricular fibrillation in vitro. *Resuscitation* **2001**, *48*, 279–291.
- 462 47. Fitzgibbon, E.; Berger, R.; Tsitlik, J.; Halperin, H.R. Determination of the noise source in the
463 electrocardiogram during cardiopulmonary resuscitation. *Critical care medicine* **2002**, *30*, S148–S153.
- 464 48. Maaten, L.v.d.; Hinton, G. Visualizing data using t-SNE. *Journal of machine learning research* **2008**,
465 *9*, 2579–2605.
- 466 49. Davies, D. DW 1979. A Cluster Separation Measure. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine*
467 *Intelligence*, pp. 224–227.
- 468 50. Vesanto, J.; Himberg, J.; Alhoniemi, E.; Parhankangas, J. SOM toolbox for Matlab 5. *Helsinki University of*
469 *Technology* **2000**, 216.
- 470 51. Isasi Liñero, I.; López de Larruzea, L.; Irusta Zarandona, U.; Aramendi Ecenarro, E. Diagnóstico del ritmo
471 cardíaco durante la resucitación cardiopulmonar mediante técnicas de aprendizaje profundo **2019**.
- 472 52. Rad, A.B.; Eftestøl, T.; Irusta, U.; Kvaløy, J.T.; Wik, L.; Kramer-Johansen, J.; Katsaggelos, A.K.; Engan, K.
473 An automatic system for the comprehensive retrospective analysis of cardiac rhythms in resuscitation
474 episodes. *Resuscitation* **2018**, *122*, 6–12.